

Proof of $P = NP$ in the P versus NP Problem

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ABSTRACT. The P versus NP problem is still open which means it is still not proved or disproved up until this day. This problem has emerged from developments of mathematical logic and electronic technology in the middle of the 20th century and it is one of the most important problems in mathematics and theoretical computer science. Although the academic consensus regarding this problem is that $P \neq NP$, in this piece of work we have gone through a different path and try to show that $P = NP$ does indeed hold. For this purpose, we have chosen the Knapsack problem which a NP-complete problem that is among the hardest of the NP problems which is verifiable in polynomial time. By adjusting the current most efficient solution algorithm with pseudo-polynomial time complexity for the NP-complete Knapsack problem by splitting up the whole problem into multiple, finite number of subproblems each with reduced polynomial time complexity we could improve the solution time of the whole NPC Knapsack problem and make it to be solvable in polynomial time as well. This proves $P = NP$ in general because all NP problems including the other subclassed NP-complete problems like e.g. the Travel salesman problem could be reduced resp. transformed to the one NP-complete problem that is the Knapsack problem for which we have discovered a solution algorithm in polynomial time.

1. Introduction

As of now, the famous P versus NP problem is still open which means it is still not conclusively proved or disproved. This problem was derived from developments of mathematical logic and electronic technology during the middle part of the 20th century. The P versus NP question is considered to be one of the most important problems in current mathematics and theoretical computer science¹.

The consensus of the academic community regarding this problem is that $P \neq NP$, not just because $P = NP$ would have enormous impact on difference branch of science like mathematics, computer science and cryptography, and also on transportation systems, weather and earth quake predictions but also because that $P \neq NP$ seems to be just more intuitive and plausible while $P = NP$ seems to good to be true and is only expected to hold in a perfect world².

In this piece of work, we do not want to go down the $P \neq NP$ path like a lot of researchers of the academic community have gone through (with mixed success) but we want to make a more comprehensive assessment and also look for possibilities of verifying the $P = NP$ statement even though this seems to be even less likely to be true. For this purpose we have reviewed many NP problems and especially NP complete resp. NPC problems which are a subclass of the NP problems and among the hardest problems in the whole NP complexity class. And if we could prove that 1 of the NP-complete problems which could be (efficiently) verified in polynomial time do also have an efficient solution algorithm in polynomial time, then the statement $NP = P$ resp. $P = NP$ would hold.

1 cf. Sipser (1992)

2 cf. Fortnow (2009)

In the next chapter 2, we will firstly choose an appropriate NP resp. NP-complete problem for deeper analysis and look at their most time efficient solution algorithm. If the solution algorithm is still not time efficient enough e.g. because it is not computable in polynomial time then we will try adjust and improve the existing solution algorithm in order to finally reduce the solution time complexity to polynomial time.

2. Proof of P = NP in the P versus NP Problem

In this important chapter, we will firstly present the current most time efficient solution for the Knapsack problem (chapter 2.1) which is a NP-complete (NPC) problem that is among the hardest problems in the whole NP complexity class. And while NP problems are those issues that could be verified in polynomial time, the P class problems are those problems which could be solved in polynomial time. Then we will deliver our proof that NP = P resp. P = NP for the NP-complete Knapsack problem (in chapter 2.2) by showing that although the Knapsack problem is at least as hard as any other NP problem (including other NP-complete problems like e.g. the Travel salesmen problem resp. TSP), if we adjust the current most time efficient solution algorithm obtained from dynamic programming accordingly, it is possible to obtain a solution to the NPC Knapsack problem in polynomial time.

The solution algorithm with polynomial time complexity for example does have the following notation:

$$O(c \cdot n^k)$$

In which n is the only dependent (input) variable (e.g. number of items to put into a knapsack) while c and k are constants resp. parameters and not input dependent (while c is a positive integer > 0 , k is ≥ 0 which is a non-negative integer).

2.1 Current most time efficient solution algorithm for the NPC Knapsack problem

Just as briefly elaborated above, while NP problems are those issues that could be verified in polynomial time, the P class problems are those problems which could be solved in polynomial time. In order to show that $P = NP$ holds under any conditions and circumstances which is the main focus of this research paper, we “just” need to show that any problem in the a subclass of the NP problems which are the NPC resp. NP-complete problems (which could be verified efficiently resp. in polynomial time) is also a P complexity class problem that could be solved efficiently resp. in polynomial time. The reasons for latter reasoning is because NPC resp. NP-complete problems are among the hardest issues to solve in the whole NP complexity class and any NP-complete problem is at least as hard as any problems in the NP class (which also includes other NP-complete problems).

The NP-complete resp. NPC problem that we have chosen is the Knapsack problem. It has multiple versions, our main interest is to deal with the classical Knapsack problem in its decision and optimization version³.

The most commonly stated version of the Knapsack problem is as follows:

Given a knapsack with capacity resp. weight W (which is a positive integer⁴) in which we could put maximally n items into it each of them having a weight w_i and value v_i (that both commonly are assumed to be a positive integer as well although mathematically the items could have zero weight and values as well which are not commonly assumed because these zero weights and values would not be meaningful), the main problem is the found out how many of the totally n items could be put into our Knapsack without exceeding the **maximum** weight capacity threshold W .

The variable n_i denotes the effective number of seleted items which is smaller than the total number of items to put into the knapsack (e.g. if the total number of items would be $n= 5$, n_i could be $3 < n = 5$ which means only 3 out of maximally 5 items could be put into the knapsack e.g. for a holiday trip).

3 The decision version of the Knapsack problem could be used to show the NP-completeness of the Knapsack problem in general including the optimization version of the Knapsack problem.

4 Although the capacity of other versions of the Knapsack problem (e.g. fractional or continuous Knapsack problem) could including fractional resp. real numbers, our key focus in this piece of work is the classical version of the Knapsack problem where for both the total weight W of the knapsack and also the weight of the single items could only take up positive integer values (mathematically the single items could have weights and values of 0 which is not that relevant in practical use cases, so we include the zero values for n and W only for mathematical completeness reasons).

The variable W_j is the effective capacity of a given knapsack which could be smaller than the maximum capacity W of an resp. any knapsack in general. When we e.g. assume that a given knapsack 1 does only have the capacity of putting items of total weight adding up to 10 kg ($= W_j = W_1$) and if we assume that each of the $n = 5$ items do have 3 kg each (and generating value of 3 kg * 2/kg = 6 value points), while there exist another knapsack no. 2 with higher capacity of e.g. 15 kg (that we assume to be the knapsack with highest capacity in our “group” of knapsacks with $W_j = W_2 = 15$ kg), so with e.g. $n_1 = n_3 = 3$ items accumulating to e.g. 3*3 kg = 9 kg (< 10 kg = W_1), we could for example generate a positive value of $10*2 = 20$ points, because we get e.g. 2 points for each additional kg taken into our knapsack and if we take the knapsack number 1 (in which we could only put in $n_1 = n_3 = 3$ items without exceeding the capacity knapsack no. 1 of 10 kg which is still ok). But if we choose the knapsack number 2 with capacity 15 kg (which is the maximum capacity of our “group” of knapsacks with $W_j = W_2 = 15$ kg) then we could put all $n = 5$ items into the larger knapsack 2 with $W_j = W_2 = 15$ kg and generating total value of 15 kg * 2 points/kg = 30 points.

While the brute force algorithm for finding these solutions of both the decision and optimization version would have exponential time complexity, more precisely $O(2^n)$ because in this case we need to try out every possibility which is not time efficient.

In order to improve the time efficiency, dynamic programming approaches are applied trying to maximize the possible items/weights/values by modifying both n_i ($\leq n$) and W_j ($\leq W$) at the same time, so that the number of effectively taken items n_i (a positive integer) is in the interval between $(0, n]$ and the knapsack weight capacity W_j (positive integer) lies between the range $(0, W]$ with W being the maximum knapsack capacity here, so that we could build a 2-dimensional n_i - W_j table with all the possible item numbers for n_i in $(0, n]$ and knapsack capacity W_j lying between the interval $(0, W]$. With this dynamic programming set up, the time efficiency resp. time complexity of the dynamic programming solution algorithm to the NP-complete Knapsack problem reduces from exponential to pseudo-polynomial⁵ to $O(n*W)$ that although the input variable n “moves” from the exponent in $O(2^n)$ to the base in $O(n*W)$, the dynamic programming solution time complexity $O(n*W)$ still depends on both input variables n (which is the maximum number of items to put into the knapsack) and W (that denotes the maximum capacity threshold of the largest possible knapsack in our “group” of knapsacks each of them having a capacity $W_j \leq W_{\max} = W$) which is still not enough to prove the NP = P statement. That is why in the next subchapter 2.2 we will evaluate whether it is possible to improve the pseudo-polynomial time efficiency which is $O(n*W)$ even more.

5 cf. i.a. 0/1 Knapsack Problem (2024), Jin (2023), Jin (2024) and He & Xu (2024) for the standard pseudo-polynomial time complexity $O(n*W)$ resp. more generically $O(a*b)$ and the pseudo-polynomial time efficiency improvements for the solution time of the Knapsack problem

2.2 Proof that $P = NP$ for the NPC Knapsack problem

As we have know from chapter 2.1, through applying the dynamic programming approach for solving the NP-complete Knapsack problem, the solution time complexity could be reduced from exponential $O(2^n)$ time complexity (only using an very inefficient brute force search algorithm) to pseudo-polynomial time complexity $O(n*W)$ which is still not enough to proof $NP = P$ resp. $P = NP$. Because while the verification time of the NPC Knapsack problem is in NP complexity class (just like all the NPC resp. NP-complete problems are), the solution time can not be included in the P class, because peusdo-polynomial time complexity $O(n*W)$ is still not really polynomial time complexity. So as the latter peusdo-polynomial time complexity $O(n*W)$ depends on 2 input variables n and W (as it is a 2-dimensional dynamic programming problem), we could ask if the time complexity could be further reduced when we would hold 1 of the 2 input variable constant (and reduce the complexity of the dynamic program to just 1 dimension resp. dependent on just 1 input variable), like the knapsack capacity W (resp. W_j) and look at each knapsack with their unique capacities W_j individually instead of looking at a range of possible knapsack capacities for multiple knapsacks resp. a group of knapsacks with an interval of capacities W taking possible values of $W_{j=1}, W_{j=2}, \dots, W_{j=k}$ lying in the range $(0, W_{j=k} = W_{\max}]$.

Thus the whole solution time complexity of originally $O(n*W)$ of the Knapsack problem applying the resp. a dynamic programming method could be split up and broken down to multiple, finite number of dynamic programming subproblems each with the following time complexities $O(n*W_{j=1}), O(n*W_{j=2}), \dots, O(n*W_{j=k})$ ⁶, which are all polynomial time complexities, because each of $W_{j=1,2,\dots,k}$ are just constants that do not vary or depend on the input variable (which is only the variable n now that denotes the number of items to include in the knapsack).

Thus the “new” time complexity of the adjusted whole knapsack problem would be the accumulated solution time of all the k subproblems that is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & O_{\text{adjusted Knapsack problem}} \\
 &= O_{\text{subproblem 1 for fixed } W_{j=1}} + O_{\text{subproblem 2 for fixed } W_{j=2}} + \dots + O_{\text{subproblem k for fixed } W_{j=k}} \\
 &= O(n*W_{j=1}) + O(n*W_{j=2}) + \dots + O(n*W_{j=k}) \\
 &= O(n*W_1) + O(n*W_2) + \dots + O(n*W_k) \\
 &= W_1 * O(n) + W_2 * O(n) + \dots + W_k * O(n) \\
 &= O(n) * [W_1 + W_2 + \dots + W_k] \\
 &= O(n) * C = O(n*C)
 \end{aligned}$$

⁶ The number of subproblems after splitting up the whole dynamic programming Knapsack problem is assumed to be finite because we assume that the weight capacities of each of the knapsacks are positive integers and thus take discrete & non-fractional resp. non-continuous values.

The calculations above shows us that the newly adjusted Knapsack problem has a polynomial solution time complexity because the new total solution time complexity $O(n \cdot C)$ is only dependent on 1 input variable n (that is the number of items to put into the knapsack), while C is just a constant and does not change when the input variable n increases or decreases. The constant C (e.g. = 100 kg) is as we could see derived from the computations above the sum of all (fixed) knapsack capacities W between an interval range $(0, W_{j=k} = W_{\max}]$ which means that the knapsack capacity variable W could take all integer values between $(0, W_{j=k} = W_{\max}]$ like for example 1, 2, 3, ..., 30 kg for instance for $W = W_{j=k} = W_{\max} = 30$ kg.

And because our newly adjusted Knapsack problem (which is a NPC resp. NP-complete problem) has polynomial solution time complexity of $O(n \cdot C)$ now depending only on 1 input variable n , it could finally be included into the P complexity class that proves the statement $NP = P$ resp. $P = NP$ ⁷. That is because we already know that the Knapsack problem, no matter in decision or optimization version, is a NP-complete problem which is among the hardest problems in the whole NP complexity class. And because of that, if we prove that 1 NP-complete problem (like the Knapsack problem) is in P class because it could be solved in polynomial time, all the other NP problems (which includes the NP-complete problems like e.g. the Travel salesman problem resp. TSP as well as the latter are a subclass of the NP problems) could be reduced resp. transformed to the single NPC resp. NP-complete problems for which we could find the solution algorithm in polynomial time that we are able to do for the Knapsack problem⁸.

7 For further research including other use cases and possibly other variations of the original Knapsack problem, we could think about whether we could also break the whole dynamic programming problem to multiple, finite subproblems by e.g. not holding the knapsack capacity W constant but the number of items n to be put into the knapsack and let the knapsack capacity W to be a variable and thus to be able to change. These could lead to interesting results as well, because our newly adjusted knapsack optimization problem would change its purpose to finding out for a given resp. fixed number of items ($= n_i$ like $n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k$) what is the smallest knapsack now - with varying capacity W (e.g. positive integer > 0) - that we could take with us in our journey to still be able to put all n_i (e.g. = 10) items into it with each of the items having an individual weight (e.g. positive integer > 0) and assigned value.

8 If we take e.g. the Travel salesman problem resp. TSP for illustration purposes, the TSP which is a NP-complete problem and thus among the hardest NP problems just like the Knapsack problem, its optimization problem version could be reduced resp. transformed to the optimization version of the Knapsack problem. Here we need to take the maximization optimization version of the Travel salesman problem by asking us how many cities could we as a traveling salesman visit for a given maximum traveling route length which is very similar resp. equivalent to the optimization version of the Knapsack problem where we try to maximize the number of items (with weights and assigned value points to each of the item) for a capacity threshold of a given knapsack to put into the knapsack. And because all NP problems including NP-complete problems like the TSP could be reduced resp. transformed to the Knapsack problem which is NPC resp. NP-complete as well, NP (incl. NPC) = P resp. $P = NP$ could be proven to be true.

We could do this by splitting up the whole dynamic program of the Knapsack problem into different subproblems and looking at each knapsack capacity W resp. $W_{j=1}, W_{j=2}, \dots, W_{j=k} = W_1, W_2, \dots, W_k$ individually for every of the broken down subproblems that are existing in finite numbers⁹ (which all has polynomial time complexity of $O(\mathbf{n} * W_j)$ because $W_j =$ e.g. W_1, W_2 etc. is only a fixed weight capacity constant now and not dependent on the input variable like e.g. $\mathbf{n}$ anymore) instead of putting a whole interval range of knapsack capacities W that are lying between $(0, W_{\max}]$ into the whole dynamic programming problem simultaneously (that would just increase the problem solving algorithm’s time complexity to $O(\mathbf{n} * \mathbf{W})$ with 2 dependent input variables $\mathbf{n}$ and $\mathbf{W}$ which was not polynomial but still pseudo-polynomial). Now when we add up all the polynomial solution times of each of the subprograms resp. subproblems that are assumed to exist in finite numbers we could finally get the solution time complexity of $O(\mathbf{n} * C)$ for the whole adjusted dynamic programming Knapsack problem which does have polynomial time complexity because now the solution time does only depend on the single input variable $\mathbf{n}$ which is the number of items to put into the knapsack.

9 As already stated, the number of subproblems after splitting up the whole dynamic programming Knapsack problem is assumed to be finite because we assume that the weight capacities of each of the knapsacks are positive integers and thus take discrete & non-fractional resp. non-continuous values.

3. Conclusion

The P versus NP problem is still open which means it is still not conclusively proved or disproved up till this day. It was derived from developments of mathematical logic and electronic technology in the middle of the 20th century. The P versus NP question is considered to be one of the most important problems in mathematics and theoretical computer science¹⁰.

The academic consensus regarding this problem is that $P \neq NP$, not just because $P = NP$ would have enormous impact on difference branch of science like mathematics, computer science and cryptography, and on transportation systems, weather and earth quake predictions but also because that $P \neq NP$ seems to be just more intuitive and plausible while $P = NP$ seems to good to be true and is only expected to hold in a perfect world¹¹.

In this piece of work, we did not go down the $P \neq NP$ path like a lot of researchers of the academic community have gone through (with mixed success) but we have looked for possibilities of verifying the $P = NP$ statement even though this seems to be even less likely to be true. For this purpose we have reviewed many NP problems and especially NP complete resp. NPC problems (which are a subclass of the NP problems and among the hardest problems in the whole NP complexity class) and if one could prove that 1 of the NP-complete problems which could be (efficiently) verified in polynomial time do also have an efficient solution algorithm in polynomial time, then the statement $NP = P$ resp. $P = NP$ would hold.

During our “journey” we have chosen the Knapsack problem as an entry point for our proof of the $P = NP$ statement. We have looked at their most time efficient solution algorithm which could be reduced from the original and very inefficient brute force algorithm with exponential time complexity $O(2^n)$ to $O(n*W)$ which is still only a pseudo-polynomial time complexity by applying a dynamic programming solution method¹² because $O(n*W)$ does still depend on both input variables n and W which is still suboptimal in our view.

10 cf. Sipser (1992)

11 cf. Fortnow (2009)

12 cf. once again i.a. 0/1 Knapsack Problem (2024), Jin (2023), Jin (2024) and He & Xu (2024) for the standard pseudo-polynomial time complexity $O(n*W)$ resp. more generically $O(a*b)$ for solution time of the Knapsack problem and its pseudo-polynomial time efficiency improvements

By splitting up the whole dynamic program to multiple subprograms resp. subproblems, we could achieve polynomial solution time complexity $O(\mathbf{n} * W_{j=k})$ for each of the k subproblems. And adding up all the (polynomial) solution time of the split subproblems in finite numbers k ¹³ which is $O(\mathbf{n} * W_{j=1}) + O(\mathbf{n} * W_{j=2}) + \dots + O(\mathbf{n} * W_{j=k})$, the time complexity of the whole dynamic program for the Knapsack problem would be

$O_{\text{adjusted Knapsack problem}}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= O_{\text{subproblem 1 for fixed } W_{j=1}} + O_{\text{subproblem 2 for fixed } W_{j=2}} + \dots + O_{\text{subproblem } k \text{ for fixed } W_{j=k}} \\
 &= O(\mathbf{n} * W_{j=1}) + O(\mathbf{n} * W_{j=2}) + \dots + O(\mathbf{n} * W_{j=k}) \\
 &= O(\mathbf{n} * W_1) + O(\mathbf{n} * W_2) + \dots + O(\mathbf{n} * W_k) \\
 &= W_1 * O(\mathbf{n}) + W_2 * O(\mathbf{n}) + \dots + W_k * O(\mathbf{n}) \\
 &= O(\mathbf{n}) * [W_1 + W_2 + \dots + W_k] \\
 &= O(\mathbf{n}) * C = O(\mathbf{n} * C)
 \end{aligned}$$

which is solvable in polynomial time that proves the statement $NP = P$ resp. $P = NP$ because the Knapsack problem is NP-complete resp. NPC which means it is among the hardest problems in the whole NP complexity class (problems that are verifiable in polynomial time). And since the NP-complete problems like the Knapsack problem is at least as hard as any other NP problem (including the other NP-complete problems like the Travel salesman problem resp. TSP), all the other NP problems including other NP-complete problems like e.g. TSP could be reduced resp. transformed to the NP-complete problem for which we have discovered a solution algorithm in polynomial time $O(\mathbf{n} * C)$ as we have done it for the Knapsack problem which proves that the statement $P = NP$ does hold.

13 As stated before, the number of subproblems (e.g. = k) after splitting up the whole dynamic programming Knapsack problem is assumed to be finite because we assume that the weight capacities of each of the knapsacks are positive integers and thus take discrete & non-fractional resp. non-continuous values.

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